

A Study of Solute-Solvent Interaction of Some Tetraalkylammonium and Alkali Metal Iodides in Ethylene Carbonate (EC) from Apparent Molal Volume Data

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Manuscript received 29 August 1975; accepted 6 December 1975

A study of solute-solvent interaction of some tetraalkylammonium and alkali metal iodides in ethylene carbonate from apparent molal volume data has been made in this communication. The slope of ϕ_v vs \sqrt{C} curves for NaI and KI in 40°-80° temperatures range and for Et₄N⁺I at 40° is positive as is the case with the common electrolytes and Me₄N⁺I in water and formamide. The slope is, in general, negative for the higher members of R₄N⁺I series similar to that in water, formamide, NMA and NMP. The negative slope in the ϕ_v vs \sqrt{C} curves of the larger R₄N⁺I salts, could be due to mutual penetration of the larger R₄N⁺ ions and their penetration by iodide ions, as has been suggested in the case of formamide, NMA and NMP. The limiting apparent molal volume, ϕ° , of salts increases with rise in temperature for R₄N⁺-iodides; however, $\frac{d\phi^\circ}{dt}$, for the smaller R₄N⁺I salts, decreases with rise in temperature, so that ϕ° vs t curves may pass through a maximum at some higher temperature and for NaI and KI, the maximum in ϕ° vs t curves occurs around 50°; appreciable ion-solvent interaction is indicated in these cases. On the other hand, for the salts containing the larger Pen₄N⁺, Hex₄N⁺ and Hep₄N⁺ ions, $\frac{d\phi^\circ}{dt}$ is almost a constant, indicating the absence of ion-solvent interaction.

In earlier studies^{1,2} on apparent molal volumes of R₄N⁺I and common salts in solvents of medium dielectric constant like DMSO, DMF & PC (ϵ_{25}° DMF = 36.71, ϵ_{25}° DMSO = 46.6, ϵ_{25}° PC = 64.92), it was found that the slope, S_v , of the ϕ_v vs \sqrt{C} curve is positive both for the R₄N⁺I and common salts without any exception. Positive slope in the ϕ_v vs \sqrt{C} curves indicates strong electrostatic ion-solvent and ion-ion interactions, the former being more effective at lower concentrations and the latter at the higher concentrations. On the other hand, in solvents of high dielectric constant, like NMA, NMP, formamide and water, studies³⁻¹⁰ indicate that the salts remain completely ionised even at fairly high concentrations resulting in weak electrostatic interactions; cation-cation and cation-anion penetration effects may give rise to a negative slope in the ϕ_v vs \sqrt{C} curves of the salts containing larger R₄N⁺ ions; the existence of negative slope for some of the common salts, containing small compact ions, in NMA and NMP, has been suggested to be due to, perhaps, the accommodation of these small ions in the voids left in the packing of the solvent molecules⁵, although for various reasons this suggestion has been questioned. It appears interesting to investigate the behaviour of R₄N⁺ and common salts in a solvent whose dielectric constant is about that of water but has no hydrogen bonding interaction as DMF, DMSO and PC. Ethylene carbonate (EC) is a very appropriate solvent of this type since its dielectric is 89.78 at 40°¹¹. It is a liquid (m.p. = 36.5°) in which there is almost a complete absence of hydrogen bonding interaction, yet it has a dielectric constant higher than that of water. Besides,

no one seems to have paid any attention to study the apparent molal volume of even the common salts in this solvent. These factors prompted us to undertake the study of the dependence of apparent molal volumes of tetraalkylammonium iodides and alkali metal iodides in EC on concentration and temperature.

Experimental

Purification of ethylene carbonate (EC) : Ethylene carbonate (Fluka, pure grade) was recrystallized three times and the liquid obtained on melting the crystals was distilled under reduced pressure. The middle fraction of the distillate was collected in dark-coloured bottles and kept in a dry box. The sample was found to melt sharply at 36.5°C and was considered pure enough for the present investigation.

Purification of tetraalkylammonium- and alkali metal iodides : The tetraalkylammonium iodides, obtained from M/s Distillation Products Industries, U.S.A., and the NaI & KI (B.D.H., A.R. grade) were purified in the usual manner. The rest of the experimental procedure for determining the density and calculating the apparent molal volume therefrom, has been reported in earlier communications.^{5,6}

Results and Discussion

From the ϕ_v data, thus obtained, ϕ_v vs \sqrt{C} curves have been drawn for different salts at various temperatures and are given in Figs. 1, 2 and 3. These plots

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Fig. 1. Apparent molal volumes of NaI and KI in ethylene carbonate at different temperatures.

Fig. 3. Apparent molal volumes of Hex₄NI and Hep₄NI in ethylene carbonate at different temperatures.

Fig. 2. Apparent molal volumes of Et₄NI, Pr₄NI, Bu₄NI and Pen₄NI in ethylene carbonate at different temperatures.

* At the higher temperatures, the slope appears to be negative for this salt also (Fig. 2).

appear to be almost straight-lines over the entire concentration range studied here and fit-in the empirical Masson's equation, namely,

$$\phi_v = \phi^{\circ} + S_v \sqrt{C}$$

The limiting apparent molal volumes, ϕ° , obtained from the extrapolation of ϕ_v vs \sqrt{C} curves to zero concentration, for different salts at various temperatures, are given in Table 1.

Dependence of apparent molal volume on concentration: As may be noted from Figs. 1-3, the slope of the ϕ_v vs \sqrt{C} curves for NaI and KI at all the temperatures and for Et₄NI at 40°* (and presumably for Me₄NI also, although this salt could not be studied due to its low solubility) is positive as is the case for common electrolytes and Me₄NI in water and formamide. The slope is, in general, negative for the higher members of the R₄NI-series similar to that in water, formamide, NMA and NMP⁸⁻⁹. It is well-known that hydrophobic R₄N⁺ - water interaction has been assumed to be responsible for the negative slope in aqueous solutions⁷. Similar type of hydrophobic interaction is not likely to be present in EC since R₄N⁺ ions and EC molecule, should be of similar nature. It appears

TABLE 1—LIMITING APPARENT MOLAL VOLUME, ϕ° , OF SOME TETRAALKYLAMMONIUM AND ALKALI METAL IODIDES IN EC AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

Salts	40°	50°	ϕ° in ml/mole at 60°	70°	80°
NaI	44.40	44.55	44.25	43.80	43.35
KI	47.35	47.80	46.80	46.24	44.80
Et ₄ NI	183.9	186.4	187.8	188.5	189.1
n-Pr ₄ NI	254.5	257.3	259.2	260.6	261.3
n-Bu ₄ NI	323.6	326.7	328.6	330.2	331.9
n-Pen ₄ NI	392.6	396.8	399.6	401.3	402.4
n-Hex ₄ NI	461.4	464.5	467.3	470.8	473.1
n-Hep ₄ NI	530.6	534.3	538.4	542.1	546.5

that the negative slope in the ϕ_v vs $1/\bar{C}$ curves of the larger R₄NI, is due to the mutual penetration of larger R₄N⁺ ions⁶⁻⁹ and their penetration by iodide ions¹⁰, as has been suggested to be the case in formamide, NMA and NMP; the penetration may become effective even at lower concentrations for the larger R₄N⁺ ions and bring about a reduction in volume and so the ϕ_v vs $1/\bar{C}$ curves have a negative slope. It would also be obvious that the negative slope producing factors would be more effective, the larger the R₄N⁺ ions and the higher the concentration. It is therefore no wonder that no positive slope in ϕ_v vs $1/\bar{C}$ curves is observed experimentally for the larger R₄NI in EC.

Effect of temperature on limiting apparent molal volume: The ϕ° values of the salts given in Table 1, have been plotted against temperature and the ϕ° vs t curves thus obtained are given in Figs. 4 and 5 from which it may be noted that for the R₄NI containing the smaller R₄N⁺ ions (Et₄N⁺, Pr₄N⁺, Bu₄N⁺), ϕ° increases with rise in temperature, although $\frac{d\phi^\circ}{dt}$, decreases, so

that ϕ° vs t curves may pass through a maximum at some higher temperature (above 80°). For NaI and KI, the maximum occurs around 50°. Hence the behaviour of NaI, KI and smaller R₄NI appears to be similar to that in aqueous solutions. On the other hand, for the salts containing the larger R₄N⁺ ions (Pen₄N⁺, Hex₄N⁺ and Hep₄N⁺), ϕ° increases almost linearly with the

rise in temperature and $\frac{d\phi^\circ}{dt}$ is approximately a constant.

It may be noted that, on account of low surface charge density on the larger R₄N⁺ ions, electrostatic interaction is expected to be negligible. However, there appears to be a high probability of some penetration of space in between the flickering or even partly coiled up four alkyl chains attached to the nitrogen atom by solvent molecules¹². The solvent molecules are slowly released and the penetration would be smaller at higher temperature and consequently, ϕ° would increase. Besides, the coiled-up chains are likely to open up at higher temperatures and this would cause the volume of the system to increase even in the absence of any penetration. Since the factors such as strong electrostatic solvation (primary solvation) which are responsible for

the decrease of $\frac{d\phi^\circ}{dt}$ at higher temperature, could not be

operative in the case of larger R₄N⁺ ions and structure breaking of the solvent would be more or less absent in the systems, ϕ° would go on increasing with temperature.

Fig. 4. Temperature dependence of limiting apparent molal volumes of NaI and KI in ethylene carbonate.

The results obtained in this investigation taken in conjunction with those already reported seem to suggest that in order that a negative slope in the ϕ_v vs $1/\bar{C}$ curves may occur, the dielectric constant of the solvent must be sufficiently high so that the salt is completely dissociated in solution and even at somewhat higher concentrations. The hydrogen bonding in the solvent does not appear to play any role in this phenomenon. If the electrostatic cation-anion interaction is strong enough to bring about ionic association which is expected when dielectric constant of the medium is suitably low, negative slope is not favoured. In some solvent of high dielectric constant e.g. water and formamide positive slope is

Fig. 5. Temperature dependence of limiting apparent molal volumes of some R_4NI salts in ethylene carbonate.

reported at very low concentrations but it becomes negative at higher concentration^{8,13}. This perhaps confirms the applicability of the theory of strong electrolytes at very low concentrations. The theory becomes ineffective when other interactions swap the electrostatic ion-ion interaction.

Acknowledgement

Financial assistance given by CSIR, India and Society of Sigma Xi USA, is gratefully acknowledged. One of us (R. K.) is thankful to the CSIR, India, for the grant of a junior research fellowship during the course of present investigations.

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